

MEDICAL SCIENCES

METHODS OF ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DISORDERS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

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Abstract

Untimely provision of orthopedic care to the population in the presence of defects in the dentition leads to the emergence of complex clinical situations caused by the development of dentoalveolar deformities. This aspect predetermines the severity in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with dentition defects.

Keywords: dentition defects, dentition deformities, orthopedic treatment, temporomandibular joint.

One of the urgent problems of orthopedic dentistry is the high prevalence of medium and large defects in the dentition among middle-aged and older people and the presence of corresponding changes in the side of the dentition, in particular occlusal disorders, dentoalveolar deformities and disorders of the temporomandibular joint and masticatory muscles [1; 2; 3]. Among the main reasons for the development of defects in the dentition, detected in more than 70% of the middle-aged population, there is a carious process and its complications, periodontal diseases, inflammatory diseases of the jaws of odontogenic and non-odontogenic origin, trauma, etc. [2]. Dental deformities, anomalies and violations of occlusal relationships play a significant role in the pathogenesis of TMJ diseases [4; 5; 6]. Therefore, patients with orthopedic pathology in combination with TMJ disorders require a specific approach in the diagnosis and choice of treatment methods that ensure the normalization of occlusal, muscle and joint ratios [7; 8; 9]. Therefore, in our time, it is necessary to carry out detailed diagnostics and take into account preliminary dental treatment in order to plan a comprehensive treatment for patients with defects in the dentition and diseases of the temporomandibular joint.

Purpose of the study: to increase efficiency and offer a detailed diagnosis of patients with dentition defects complicated by disorders of the temporomandibular joint.

Materials and methods of research

52 patients with dentition defects, dentoalveolar deformities and disorders of the temporomandibular joint were examined. All patients used general clinical methods of examination: complaints, anamnesis, extraoral and intraoral examination, palpation, percussion, probing. An "Examination Map" was developed, in which the proposed sections of a detailed dental examination were included, as well as a history of periodontal treatment, endodontic treatment, orthodontic treatment, orthopedic treatment, and analysis of vertical, sagittal, and transversal mandibular movements. Dental defects were diagnosed according to the Kennedy classification, and temporomandibular disorders -

according to the classification of B. Neville, D. Damm, S. Allen, J. Buukot (1995). We studied the state and localization of defects in the dentition, the degree of tooth mobility, the degree of atrophy of the alveolar process, the state of hard tissues of the teeth; analyzed diagnostic models; X-ray methods were used, as well as condilography using a dental articulation system and a 3SHAPE 3D scanner.

Research results

On examination of patients, 43 patients had lateral included defects in the dentition and 9 included in the frontal area and connected in the lateral and frontal areas. Using the "Examination Map" developed by us, we found that 55% of patients knew the endodontic history, and only 36.7% knew the details. In general, 70% of the surveyed knew about the periodontal history, and 28.3% knew more about it. 33.3% knew about preliminary orthodontic treatment, and young patients knew more (21.7%). The highest percentage was the information of patients about orthopedic treatment - 83.3%, and 61.7% of the surveyed knew in detail about the features of the provided preliminary orthopedic treatment. It should be noted that the least of all dentists ask patients about the condition and diseases of the temporomandibular joint, this percentage was 16.7%, but only 13.3% of patients could provide accurate data. The results obtained indicate insufficient attention when examining patients with defects in the dentition associated with dentoalveolar deformities, on the state of the temporomandibular joints and, accordingly, the occlusal ratio. Studying the state of the TMJ and masticatory muscles, we took into account the maximum opening and S-shaped displacements, pain during vertical movements of the lower jaw; with sagittal movements of the lower jaw - limited or unlimited; with transversal - symmetry and blocked or not blocked movements of the TMJ. We have identified the following features of the clinic when examining the temporomandibular joint according to the proposed map: 53.3% of patients experience periodic stiffness and limitation of movements in the evening; 8.3% of patients have a crunch; 36.7%

of patients lower their jaw in an S-shape; 35.0% of patients have limitation of sagittal movements at h/h; 31.7% of patients have transversal restriction of movements of the n / w and 26.7% of patients experience pain on palpation of the joints. We found that 49 examined patients (91.7%) had temporomandibular joint disorders with manifestations of TMJ dysfunction. On the basis of the results obtained according to the "Patient Examination Card" proposed for use with detailed dental anamnesis to identify disorders of the dentition and TMJ disorders in patients with defects in the dentition, we proposed an algorithm for treating patients, including temporary structures, caps and modern aesthetic prosthetics. After a detailed subjective and objective examination, taking into account the previous medical history, an algorithm for treating patients was proposed, providing for the manufacture of temporary structures to replace defects in the dentition and stabilize the position of the articular heads of the lower jaw based on condillography for a period of 2-6 months. Models are studied in the 3SHAPE 3D scanner using Aqualizer. After stabilization of the TMJ condition, we produce permanent modern aesthetic ceramic-metal structures or based on zircon dioxide.

Defects in the dentition and hard tissues of the teeth can lead to the development of periodontal diseases, deformations of the dentition, violation of occlusal relationships. Detailing the methods of preliminary treatment and diagnosis of patients, taking into account the state of the temporomandibular joint, will make it possible to draw up a further plan for the examination and complex treatment of patients with defects in the dentition, complicated by dentoalveolar deformities and TMJ disorders.

Conclusions

We have found that the detailed examination and diagnosis of patients, especially the anamnesis of preliminary treatment, will allow an objective assessment of the state of the dentoalveolar system and draw up a comprehensive treatment plan. However, only 13.3%-61.7% of those surveyed have detailed information about the preliminary stages and methods of dental treatment. The results obtained indicate a lack of attention when examining patients with dentition defects associated with dentoalveolar deformities, the state of the temporomandibular joints and, accordingly, occlusal relationships. In particular, in 53.3% of patients, stiffness and limitation of movements of the lower jaw in the evening are observed periodically; 36.7% of pa-

tients lower the lower jaw in an S-shape; 35.0% of patients have limitation of sagittal and 31.7% of transversal movements of the mandible. These results indicate the presence of a syndrome of painful articular or joint-muscular dysfunction. On the basis of the results obtained, we proposed an algorithm for the complex treatment of patients, including the study of models in the 3SHAPE 3D scanner, the use of temporary structures, caps, and modern aesthetic prosthetics.

References

1. Rozhko M.M. Ortopedicheskaia stomatologija: uchebnik /M.M. Rozhko, V.P. Besprjad'ko. – K.: Kniga pljus,2003. – 552 s.
2. Terapevticheskaia stomatologija: uchebnik: v 4 t. – T. 3. Zabolevanie parodonta/[M.F. Danilevskij,A.V. Borisenko, A.M. Politun i dr.]. – M.: Medicina, 2008. – 616 s.
3. Zablockij Ja.V. Rasprostranennost' i strukturadefektov zubnyh rjadov u naselenija L'vova I L'vovskoj oblasti/Ja.V. Zablockij, N.M. Didik// Vestnik stomatologii. – 2005. – № 4. – С. 77 – 87.
4. Hvatova V. Osnovy gnatologii. Lechenie zabolevanij i disfunkcij visochno-nizhnecheljustnogo sustava / V. Hvatova // DentArt. – 2010. – № 1. – S.28 – 40.
5. Maksimenko P.V. Uovershenstvovanie differencirovannyh podhodov k ortopedicheskomu lecheniju pacientov s zabolevanijami parodonta/P.V. Maksimenko //Integrativnaja antropologija. – 2010. – № 1 (15). – S.31 – 35.
6. Trofimenko E.A. Pokazateli mikrocirkuljacii I klinicheskaia charakteristika sostojanija tkanej parodonta v lic s defektami zubnyh rjadov/O.A. Trofimenko // Ukrainskij stomatologicheskij al'manah. – 2006. – № 6. – S. 19 – 22.
7. Moskalenko P.A. Okkluzionno-kompresionnye narushenija komponentov visochno-nizhnecheljustnogo sustava pri ego odnostoronnem vyvihe / P.A.Moskalenko, O.V. Rybalov // Ukrainskij stomatologicheskij al'manah. – 2009. – № 3. – S. 9 – 11.
8. Nesprjad'ko V.P. Ustranenie okkluzionnyh narushenij pacientov s poterej pervyh postojannyh moljarov kakjetap podgotovki k ortopedicheskomu lecheniju / V.P.Nesprjad'ko, G.E. Zaharova, P.Ju. Prokop'eva // Nauchnyj vestnik NMU im. O.A. Bogomol'ca. – 2009. –№ 2 – 3. – S. 124 – 128.
9. Hvatova V.A. Okkluzionnye shiny/V.A. Hvatova, S.A. Chikunov. – M.: MIG «Medicinskaja kniga», 2010. – 56 s.